

CDIO INTEGRATED LEARNING EXPERIENCES IN PROCESS SAFETY USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract

This paper shares the work done in using digital technologies – namely Interactive Video and Digital Twin – to development process safety awareness among students from the Diploma in Chemical Engineering, Singapore Polytechnic. The work involved the creation of 2 “virtual plants” that replicates 2 actual physical pilot plants in the workshop. This work is part of a greater initiative to inculcate a safety mindset among our students, so that they can work effectively as process technicians in the chemical processing industry. In these activities, students are required to use a plant’s Piping and Instrumentation Diagram (P&ID) to carry out line-tracing, and identify potential process safety hazards. These “virtual plants” provide students more opportunity to learn at their own pace, and not subjected to the rigidity of workshop opening hours to perform the task with the physical plants. In later part of the semester, they are required to physically operate various pilot plants, and their skills in performing line-tracing effectively and identifying various process safety hazards will be put to the test. The development work is timely, as the Covid-19 pandemic can result in prolonged campus closure, jeopardising students’ learning opportunities in accessing the physical pilot plants. The software packages also helped address any applicable needs for safe distancing. As events unfolded, when the 2 software packages are ready for use, students were permitted to return to campus for activities that require physical presence. Hence, in the pilot run, the author managed to engage the students in using the 2 software packages in the workshop; and then to visit the physical plants to make a quick comparison of the two modes of learning. This paper first briefly shares the importance of process safety, and explains how integrated learning experiences are designed using the CDIO Framework (www.cdio.org) with core principles of learning as guidance. This paper also shares students learning experience with the 2 software packages, and shed some lights into their preferences, most notably in terms of delivery mechanism in the event of campus closure: either in synchronous or asynchronous manner.

Keywords: *Process Safety, CDIO, Interactive Video, Digital Twin, Integrated Learning Experiences*

Importance of Process Safety

Safety is of paramount importance in the chemical processing industries, given that they deal with many different chemicals of various toxicity many of which are also flammable; and often at high temperatures and pressures. Broadly speaking, safety can be classified into workplace safety (also known as personal safety or occupational safety) and chemical process safety (or just process safety in short). Most people are more familiar with workplace hazards, which are often visible and readily perceived and understood; the nature and scale of a potential injury – for example from a fall – is easy to imagine. Process hazards on the other hand, are less intuitive, so hazard identification techniques need to be structured. Although some process hazards might be easily perceived, such as leakage of chemical from a corroded pipe work for example, many hazards are not so visible and not intuitive – for example, the sequence of events following a loss of containment whether due to human error (such as not following operating procedures) or equipment failure.

Process Safety: Line-tracing using P&ID

Teaching of process safety is integrated into the practical in the core module *Laboratory and Process Skills 2 (LPS2)*, taught to Year 1 Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) students in Semester 2. This module is part of a suite of 4 skills-based modules in the revised DCHE course structure featuring a spiral curriculum (Cheah & Yang, 2018). Besides developing skills in laboratory analysis and process plant operations, these modules also serve to inculcate in students a safety mindset (Yang & Cheah, 2020). Safety awareness in laboratory setting had already been instilled in Year 1 Semester 1 in *Laboratory and Process Skills 1*, where students learn about Job Safety Analysis and using the correct personal protective equipment, a key aspect of workplace safety. In *LPS2* they are now required to learn about process safety, before operating various pilot plants to gain experience as process technicians. Teaching of

process safety takes place alongside the students' learning of Piping and Instrumentation Diagram (P&ID) and line-tracing, 2 key competencies for process technicians.

The P&ID is the blueprint of a chemical plant, it uses symbols to represent how the actual plant will be constructed, for every plant item ranging from equipment to valves and instruments, to all pipes, piping components and fittings. Line-tracing is the process whereby a chemical engineer or process technician uses a P&ID and literally "walk the line" in the plant, checking every item in the plant against that shown in the P&ID. Every discrepancy noted shall need to be reconciled. Line-tracing is useful not only in helping an engineer or technician get familiar with a given chemical plant, it is also serving an important role in promoting critical thinking necessary in understanding process safety. When tracing a line, the engineer or technician needs to know what is flowing inside the pipe (gas, liquid, or mixture), their properties (such as flammability, corrosivity, etc), operating conditions (mainly pressure and temperature, among other process variables), the direction of flow from equipment to equipment and the changes that happened (e.g. reaction, heating or cooling, or phase changes, treatment, separation, etc), sampling and/or sample collection points, any deliberate or potential discharge, for every pipe in the chemical plant.

Having a safety mindset during line-tracing is essential for the engineer or technician to "see the unseen" (Abramowicz, et al, 2019). Having complete knowledge at any given line is important during normal operation, should a process upset (e.g. flange leak, pump seal failure, etc) happened. During operation, a valve may be wrongly opened or closed, so one needs to be aware of the potential consequences of such mal-operation. During plant shutdown where maintenance works need to be carried out, line-tracing is important to ensure that proper positive isolations had been carried out, so that there will be no accidental ingress of chemicals. Proper line-tracing also ensure that all necessary sections of the pipes (and equipment) are properly drained of chemicals and purged free of any harmful hydrocarbons.

What are Integrated Learning Experiences?

Standard 7 Integrated Learning Experiences is one of the 12 Core Standards in the CDIO Framework (www.cdio.org) used to guide curricular design or redesign. More specifically, it is stated that "*Integrated learning experiences are pedagogical approaches that foster the learning of disciplinary knowledge simultaneously with personal and interpersonal skills, and product, process, system, and service building skills. They incorporate professional engineering issues in contexts where they coexist with disciplinary issues. For example, students might consider the analysis of a product, the design of the product, as well as the social, economic and environmental responsibility of the designer of the product, all in one learning experience.*"

In the context of this work, the integrated learning experiences combined within the same the learning setting the simultaneous application of technical know-how of reading a P&ID, using it to conduct line-tracing, and identifying potential process safety hazards, all at the same time integrating teamwork, communication, critical thinking and self-directed learning.

What are Core Principles of Learning?

There are various versions for core principles of learning being suggested. Here, the author uses Sale's 10 Core Principles of Learning (Sale, 2015), as shown in Table 1. Sale's core principles of learning are based on his extensive review of the literature on human learning and studies on effective teaching professionals in a range of educational contexts. The author adapted these principles to the context of teaching and learning using digital technologies. This was done via a literature review on the affordances of digital technologies in enhancing teaching and learning (Gadera & Zalipour, 2018; Brame, 2016; Kolas, 2015; Willmot, et al. 2012; Karppinen, 2005; Mayer & Gallini, 1990) identifying and aligning the findings to one or more core principles of learning, thereby integrating various best practices into a holistic approach towards an integrated learning experience for students.

Table 1. Sale's Core Principles of Learning

S/N	Core Principle of Learning
01	Learning goals, objectives and proficiency expectations are clearly visible to learners
02	Learners prior knowledge is activated and connected to new learning
03	Content is organized around key concepts and principles that are fundamental to understanding the structure of a subject
04	Good thinking promotes the building of understanding
05	Motivational strategies are incorporated into the design of learning experiences
06	Learning design takes into account the working of memory systems
07	Instructional methods and presentation mediums engage the range of human of senses
08	A psychological climate is created which is both success-orientated and fun
09	The development of expertise requires deliberate practice
10	Assessment practices are integrated into the learning design to promote desired learning outcomes and provide quality feedback

Design of Integrated Learning Experiences using Interactive Video and Digital Twin

Teaching of identifying process safety hazards via line-tracing is achieved via the design of 2 integrated learning experiences, one using digital twin (DT) and another

using interactive video (IV). The DT package is modelled after a neutralizing reactor pilot plant (see Figures 1 and 2), while the IV package is modelled after a shell-and-tube heat exchanger pilot plant (see Figures 3 and 4), both available in our workshop. Both are designed by applying the core principles of learning, to provide sufficient interactivity to engage students in their learning. Both requires students to use the plant's P&ID to carry out “virtual” line-tracing, where they first learnt of process safety hazards using the DT package, and 1 week later use the IV package to identify these hazards.

Figure 1. Actual Neutralizing Reactor Plant

Figure 2. Digital Twin of Neutralizing Reactor Plant

Figure 3. Actual Shell-and-Tube Heat Exchanger Plant

Figure 4. P&ID for Shell-and-Tube Heat Exchanger Plant

The rationale for using the neutralizing reactor is a straight-forward one. Neutralization is a concept already understood by all students from studying chemistry during their secondary schools. The choice of using a heat exchanger is also straight-forward: it is a common equipment used in every chemical plant: to heat or cool either gas or liquid streams or mixture of both to the desired operating temperature. As in operating any chemical plant, skills such as critical thinking, teamwork and communication are essential; not only to ensure successful start-up, shutdown, or normal operation of the plant. In this aspect, paying careful attention to potential process safety hazards is of paramount importance.

The rest of this section provide explanations on how the relevant CDIO Standards and Core Principles of Learning (CoP) are used to guide the design of the 2 integrated learning experiences (CDIO Standard 7).

CDIO Standard 1 (The Context) sets the scene for learning, i.e. students working as process technicians in a chemical plant. The learning outcomes (CDIO Standard 2 Learning Outcomes) are clearly defined in terms of desired performance standards and clearly communicated to students (CoP#1). The competency to be developed is structured for progressive development (CDIO Standard 3 Integrated Curriculum). Learner prior knowledge of P&ID reading and table-top line-tracing covered in earlier lessons in *LPS2* (Cheah, 2021) are activated to support new learning of identifying potential process hazards (CoP#2). To assist students in assimilating the new knowledge, all activities in both packages are broken down into manageable “chunks”, and arranged in a logical sequence centred around key concepts that helps students understand the topics (CoP#3). In addition, a workbook was developed for each learning task to scaffold students learning (CoP#3) as they go through the package, with the help of guiding questions (Lawson, et al, 2006). Through careful scaffolding and sequencing of the activities, these workbooks helped with the “chunking” efforts to reduce students’ cognitive loads (Schwan, & Riempp, 2004). Prompts are used throughout both packages and the workbooks to stimulate thinking (CoP#4) and hints are provided as appropriate (CoP#5). Another motivational

strategy came from the choice of neutralizing reactor plant itself. This plant has 4 storage tanks and correspondingly 4 centrifugal pumps, and hence the lecturer did the teaching of line-tracing using P&ID based on one set of tank and pump; and to demonstrate how process safety hazards can be identified. Students then get to practice this using different sets of tank and pump for slight different operation (CoP#9). This serves to enhance their motivation that they can successfully complete the task assigned (CoP#8). When the students move on to the IV package, they are then challenged to identify (CoP#4) new process hazards under a different context, as the equipment plant they will work on, namely the shell-and-tube heat exchanger, is not found in the neutralizing reactor plant.

Interactivities (Vural, 2013; Wouters, et al, 2007; Zhang, et al, 2006) introduced throughout the packages include a variety of methods, such as true or false questions, multiple choice questions, fill-in-the-blanks, move-the-mouse-and-click, drag-and-drop, etc. Some of these allows multiple attempts; and feedback are provided for both right and wrong answers. Herein lies the big advantage of using digital technologies: feedback can be given in a targeted and timely manner (Richtberg & Girwidz, 2019). More specifically, with regards to identifying potential process hazards, students are asked “what if” questions, using a template prescribed by the Singapore Workplace Safety & Health Council (WSHC, 2017). This approach requires that students first imagine how one would perform a task, before actually executing it (Kubovy, 1983). This will require students to integrate their generic knowledge on process safety hazards analysis and apply them in the specific operational context of a given chemical plant. Constructive alignment is applied to ensure that the assessment of their learning is based on their completion of the template.

Discussions of Student Learning Experience

As mentioned in the earlier section, students first went through the activities using DT, with the lecturer facilitating the line-tracing process and process safety hazards identification. Students record their learning in the workbook. In the following week, they carry out the process on their own guided by narratives in the IV and the workbook.

The initial intent of this work is to use digital technologies to complement student learning. As we are all too familiar, the Covid-19 pandemic had disrupted learning, including this development work. Indeed the campus was closed for a prolonged period and all lessons had to be conducted online. As events unfolded, when the 2 software packages are ready for use, students were permitted to return to campus for work in laboratories or workshops, subjected to proper safe management measures. Hence, in the pilot run, the author managed to engage the students in using the 2 software packages in the workshop; and then to visit the physical plants to make a quick comparison of the two modes of learning.

To assess students’ learning experience in using the 2 packages, we conducted a survey after the conclusion of the 2 learning activities. The survey used a combination of close-ended questions using 5-point Likert Scale; and several open-ended questions. A total of 83 students responded to the survey, out of 110 students from 6 classes; representing a response rate of 75.45%. The findings are shown in Figures 5 to 8.

The large percentages of students who rated the DT and IV as useful (Figure 5) for helping them with the intended learning outcomes (Figure 6) are encouraging. Such results reinforced earlier findings from cognitive psychology, for example the works of Shepard & Cooper (1982) who had made the connection between visual clues, the memory process, and knowledge acquisition.

Figure 5. Usefulness of DT in learning process safety

Figure 6. Usefulness of learning tasks using DT and IV

Figure 7. Usefulness of narratives in IV

Figure 8. Perception of replacing using virtual plant vs physical plant for learning

Does this mean that the DT and IV packages can be used to replace actual on-site activities should the need for campus closure arise again? Even though a large majority of students agree that the line tracing experience using digital technologies are realistic enough to help them with their learning (Figure 7), this percentage dropped significantly when asked if these activities were to be carried out entirely online (Figure 8).

The survey also contains open-ended questions, one of which asked students to indicate and explain their preference, if any, for using DT or IV. Another question asked them for their preference, in the event that they had to learn from home, which mode of learning – synchronous or asynchronous. Only 19 students responded with entries to the open-ended questions, of which only 16 provided useful replies whereby a combinations of IV and DT is preferred. The reasons they provided confirmed what the author had intuitively knew about 'limitations' of IV vs. DT. The majority of these students (10 vs 6) also stated that they prefer the asynchronous approach; with many citing the ability to work at their own pace as the main reason. Those who prefer a synchronous approach mentioned opportunity to seek clarifications with lecturer as the main reason for their selection.

Moving Ahead and Plans for Improvement

The introduction of these learning activities was very timely indeed, as these software packages can be used should the campus be closed again in the future. Even if access to campus is permissible, the software packages can be used alongside the actual pilot plants, and can help to address any applicable needs for safe distancing. More

importantly, given the students strong reservation of using the DT and IV as substitute for in-campus learning, and in the event that online learning still becomes necessary, preference for asynchronous learning; the author now contemplates the use of hybrid mode of learning moving forward for the next run of the module.

The author recognizes that there will always exist trade-offs in students' learning when contents best learnt via hands-on are moved completely in online format. This is particularly so for process technicians, as expertise or mastery results from physical presence in the chemical plant that engages all 5 senses. Technological developments in virtual reality (VR) held promises to enhance these, but needs to be supported by 5G network to overcome bandwidth constraint with respect to latency issues. Besides sights and sounds, there are still limitations of what digital technologies can simulate in terms of smell (e.g. the uniqueness of chlorine gas), or touch (e.g. tightness of a closed valve). Response in real-time is in particular an important considerations, especially in emergency situation; and the mere clicking of a mouse or dragging a slider to simulate valve opening will convey the wrong understanding to learners in actual time and effort needed.

Next, on the improvement of the 2 packages. The first iteration of the DT and IV packages is by no means perfect. Even before introducing them to students, the author had already noted many areas that can be improved on the prototypes developed, as new ideas that popped-up when he reviewed the package. As the Covid-19 pandemic is looming, the author decided to go ahead with the package, noting down the deficiencies to be improved upon in later iteration of the packages when the opportunity is available. It may not be so easy if a new programmer is tasked to carry out updates of packages done earlier by different person(s).

It is also worth noting that the DT package developed is only considered as a "basic-level" one, in that only the physical aspects of the pilot plant had been converted into digital version. The interactivities are created to depict visually how a fluid will flow in the plant, but these were not modelled mathematically as would be the case with a dynamic simulation system. Work is in progress to build another digital twin using a more complex pilot plant for Year 2 DCHE students. Due to budgetary constraint, the new digital twin package under development can only feature dynamic modelling that are still limited to that of "first principles" only, meaning that the modelling is only up to the "macro" level as predicted by the laws of thermodynamics. The model still does not have the high-level fidelity down to mimicking the behaviour of individual equipment. For example, in the case of valve opening, the model is not able to discern differences in valve characteristics, which affects how much a fluid can pass through based on the valve opening. Such application is an important consideration in guiding valve selection for emergency operation. Unlike the DT described in this paper, the new digital twin will be 2-dimensional in nature, again due to cost constraint. It

therefore is not capable of delivering the 3-D immersive experience as can be provided by VR.

Conclusions

This paper shared the learning points gained from designing integrated learning experiences for students to develop safety mindset in chemical plant operations using digital twin and interactive video. Feedback from students indicated that they prefer to use them to complement traditional on-site learning, rather than completely online.

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